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RECOGNITION AND ENFORCEMENT OF FOREIGN JUDGMENTS IN CIVIL AND COMMERCIAL MATTERS: THE NORMATIVE CROSSROADS IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

Abstract: *The recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BH) is primarily governed by the Private International Law Act of 1982, which was inherited from the former Yugoslavia. Additionally, there are many bilateral agreements in force in BH that deal with international legal assistance. As BH is a candidate for EU membership, it is important to consider the relationship between the relevant provisions of the Brussels I Recast Regulation and the law of third countries including BH. This will help to create a normative solution for mutual recognition of foreign court decisions. The authors will focus on the exorbitant bases of jurisdiction in the national systems of individual EU member states and the possibility of recognizing such decisions in BH.*

Keywords: *Recognition and Enforcement, BH PIL Act, Brussels I Regime, Hague Convention 2019, exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction.*

1. Introduction

Bosnia and Herzegovina is at a normative crossroads in terms of its legislative activity in the area of recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments. It is still primarily regulated by the provisions of the Law on the Resolution of Conflicts of Laws with the Regulations of Other Countries in

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Certain Relationships (further in the text: BH PIL Act), which was passed back in 1982 in the former Yugoslavia¹ and adopted into the legal system of Bosnia and Herzegovina, after its independence in 1992.² Due to political reasons, it seems quite likely that the existing BH PIL Act will be the basic source of law for some time to come.³ It is therefore important to chase alternative ways of modernizing the rules of private international law in Bosnia and Herzegovina. In the first part of the paper, the authors analyze internal and international sources in the field of recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments and the possibilities offered by these legal sources in terms of preventing the effect of judgments in BH based on the exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction of foreign courts. Analyzing the provisions of the Brussels I Recast regime, in the second part of the article, the authors point out that this Regulation does not apply to defendants from third countries, but the national rules of the EU member states, including the exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction, which they especially explain using the example of *forum arresti* of Dutch law. Finally, the conclusion contains proposals for overcoming the problem of recognition of such decisions in Bosnia and Herzegovina through the mechanisms of bilateral cooperation, the extension of the Brussels I Recast regime to defendants from third countries, and accession to the Hague Convention from 2019.

¹ Stanivuković, M., Živković, M., *Međunarodno privatno pravo – opšti deo*, Službeni glasnik, 2010., p. 38; Šaula, V., *Osnovi međunarodnog privatnog prava Republike Srpske*, Pravni fakultet Univerziteta u Banjoj Luci, 2011., p. 56; Katičić, N., Matić, Ž., Sajko, K., *Teze za Zakon o međunarodnom privatnom pravu i postupku sa obrazloženjem*, Prinosi, br. 3/70, p. 3-40; Katičić, N., Matić, Ž., Sajko, K., *Teze za Zakon o međunarodnom privatnom pravu i postupku*, Prinosi, br. 6/73, p. 1-84; On this Law and need for its change see in: Alihodžić, J., Duraković, A., *Zakon o međunarodnom privatnom pravu u Bosni i Hercegovini – retrospektiva i perspektiva normativnog uređenja*, Zbornik radova Pravnog fakulteta u Tuzli, br. 1, 2023, p. 53-72; Alihodžić, J., *Razvoj evropskog međunarodnog privatnog prava: pravci reforme zakonodavstva u Bosni i Hercegovini*, OFF-SET, Tuzla, 2012, p. 219 – 223.

² *Ibid.*, p. 219.

³ On the impossibility of carrying out reform in this area and alternative ways of modernizing the rules of private international law in Bosnia and Herzegovina: Alihodžić, J., Meškić, Z., Duraković, A., *Accepting EU Private International Law Standards into the Legal System of Bosnia and Herzegovina: What Can be Done While Waiting for Godot?* LeXonomica – Journal of Law and Economics, Vol. 11, No 2, 2019, p. 151-174.

2. Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Court Judgments in Bosnia and Herzegovina

The recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments in BH is carried out in accordance with the system of limited control of judicial acts,⁴ which implies that the competent authorities will examine whether the foreign judgment meets the requirements prescribed by law.⁵ Besides judgments *stricto sensu*, the notion of judgment also includes court settlements concluded before a foreign court, and decisions of other authorities that are equated with a court judgment and a settlement in the country where they were made. Following definition from Article 86, recognition will occur on the assumption that the conditions from article 87 – 92 of the BH PIL Act are met.^{6/7} Finally, the same provisions are applied to the enforcement of a foreign court decision, with the obligation of the applicant to submit also a certificate of its enforceability under the law of the country in which it was made.⁸ Given the complex constitutional organization of Bosnia and Herzegovina,⁹ the courts responsible for the recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments are the Cantonal Courts in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina,¹⁰ regional courts in the Republic of Srpska¹¹ and the Basic Court of Brčko District.¹² Pursuant to the provision of Article 101 of the BH PIL Act, if no special decision has been made on the recognition of a foreign judgment, any court may decide on the recognition of that decision in the procedure as a preliminary issue, but with effect only for that procedure. It is

⁴ Muminović, E., *Procesno međunarodno privatno pravo*, Pravni fakultet Univerziteta u Sarajevu, 2006., p. 83-84.

⁵ Article 86-96 BH PIL Act.

⁶In Bosnia and Herzegovina, the system of assumed reciprocity is accepted. Alihodžić, J., *Princip „pretpostavljenog“ reciprociteta u funkciji efikasne realizacije međunarodne pravne pomoći u zemljama regiona*, Zbornik radova „Regionalna saradnja u oblasti građanskog sudskog postupka sa međunarodnim elementom“, Banjaluka, 2009., p. 189-204.

⁷The provisions of Article 93 - 95 of the BH PIL Act are not relevant for this area, since they refer to the issue of the personal status of domestic and foreign citizens.

⁸Article 96 BH PIL Act. Dika, M., Knežević, G., Stojanović, S., *Komentar Zakona o međunarodnom privatnom i procesnom pravu*, Nomos, Beograd 1991., p. 317.

⁹Alihodžić, J., (2012), p. 219 – 221.

¹⁰Article 28. paragraph 2. point e) Law on Courts in FBH, Official Gazette FBH No. 38/2005, 22/2006, 63/2010, 72/2010-correction., 7/2013, 52/2014 i 85/2021.

¹¹Article 31. paragraph 3. point d) Law on Courts RS, Official Gazette RS No. 37/2012, 14/2014-decision of CC, 44/2015, 39/2016 – Decision of CC, 100/2017.

¹²Article 21. paragraph 4. point f) Law on Courts Brčko District, Official Gazette BD BH, No. 18/2020 – consolidated version.

important to note that this law does not contain a provision that would prevent the recognition of foreign court judgments based on exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction. However, there are opinions that the recognition could be refused even if there was no exclusive jurisdiction of the domestic court, if the assumptions for the jurisdiction of the foreign court were absurd, by appealing to public order.¹³ However, bearing in mind the wording of Article 91 BH PIL Act, which stipulates that a foreign court decision will not be recognized if it contradicts the Constitution of Bosnia and Herzegovina and the established foundations of social order,¹⁴ it is unlikely that in practice there would be a refusal to recognize a foreign court decision based on exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction.¹⁵ For the sake of legal certainty and uniform judicial practice in Bosnia and Herzegovina on this matter, it would be good during the eventual reform of the BH PIL Act to introduce an explicit rule that prevents the recognition and enforcement of a foreign court decision based on exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction. Such a provision is foreseen in the reform laws of Montenegro¹⁶ and North Macedonia.¹⁷ Although the BH PIL Act is considered the basic source of law in this area, its application will not occur if a specific legal issue that falls within the scope of this law is regulated by another law or international convention.¹⁸ Given that a significant number of bilateral agreements on international legal assistance in civil (and criminal) matters¹⁹ are in force in Bosnia and Herzegovina, some of which contain provisions on mutual recognition and enforcement of court judgments

¹³ Dika, M., Knežević, G., Stojanović, S., *op. cit.*, p. 292.

¹⁴ Authors adjusted the original text of the provision.

¹⁵ In practice, the activity of the competent court or other body in BH is limited to checking whether for that specific legal matter that was resolved by a foreign decision there is the exclusive jurisdiction of authorities in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

¹⁶ Article 145 of the PIL Act of Montenegro („Official Gazette of Montenegro“, No. 1/2014, 6/2014 – correction., 11/2014 – correction., 14/2014 i 47/2015) states: „A foreign court decision will not be recognized if a foreign court has based its international jurisdiction on facts that the law of Montenegro does not provide for establishing the international jurisdiction of a Montenegrin court to resolve the same dispute“.

¹⁷ Article 161 of the PIL of Republic of North Macedonia (Official Gazette of RNM No. 32 from 10.2.2020) states: „A foreign court decision will not be recognized if the foreign court based its jurisdiction on circumstances that are not provided for by this or other law to establish the jurisdiction of a court or other body of the Republic of North Macedonia to resolve that type of dispute with an international element.“

¹⁸ Article 3. BH PIL Act.

¹⁹ On bilateral agreements in force in BH: http://www.mpr.gov.ba/organizacija_nadleznosti/medj_pravna_pomoc/bilateralni_ugovori/Konvencije.aspx?langTag=bs-BA, page access 12.10.2023.

between contracting states, as well as a certain number of agreements that directly regulate recognition and enforcement of court judgments in civil and commercial matters, these bilateral agreements will have priority in application in relation to the relevant provisions of the BH PIL Act. Some of these contracts were adopted into the legal system of Bosnia and Herzegovina by notification of succession after the dissolution of Yugoslavia,²⁰ while some were concluded by Bosnia and Herzegovina after gaining independence.²¹ Therefore, when it comes to bilateral agreements from the former Yugoslavia, it is important to check with the Ministry of Justice of Bosnia and Herzegovina the issue of its validity.²² For the purposes of this paper, it is important to conduct research on whether some of them contain a rule that enables the refusal of recognition and enforcement of the foreign judgment based on exorbitant jurisdiction.²³ Thus, some agreements previously concluded by the former Yugoslavia, which were adopted into the legal system of Bosnia and Herzegovina by notification of succession,²⁴ contain a provision that prevents the recognition and enforcement of the foreign judgment on the basis of exorbitant jurisdiction.²⁵

²⁰ http://www.mpr.gov.ba/organizacija_nadleznosti/medj_pravna_pomoc/bilateralni_ugovori/default.aspx?id=939&langTag=bs-BA, page access 12.10.2023.

²¹ http://www.mpr.gov.ba/organizacija_nadleznosti/medj_pravna_pomoc/bilateralni_ugovori/ugovori/default.aspx?id=3813&langTag=bs-BA, page access 12.10.2023.

²² Živković, M., Marjanović, S., *Nekoliko pitanja u vezi s primjenom međunarodnih ugovora u međunarodnom privatnom pravu Republike Srbije*, Pravni vjesnik, god. 35, br. 3-4, 2019., p. 280.

²³ It is also important to point out that the aforementioned bilateral agreements on international legal assistance in civil (and criminal) matters have a rather uneven approach to the regulation of certain issues of international/cross-border cooperation, which has the consequence that some of them do not contain a section on the recognition and enforcement of foreign judicial decisions at all.

²⁴ The authors received information about the validity of the contracts listed in this text, which contain the rule on refusing to recognize judgments made on the basis of exorbitant jurisdiction, from the competent Ministry of Justice of Bosnia and Herzegovina on November 10, 2023.

²⁵ Article 3 of the Convention between the Government of the SFRY and the Government of the French Republic on the Recognition and Enforcement of Court Judgments in Civil and Commercial Matters ("Official Gazette of the SFRY - International Agreements and Other Agreements", No. 7/72) reads: Decisions made by the court of one contracting party are recognized or declared enforceable in the territory of the other party:

a) if the court of origin was competent according to the law of the requested state or based on the convention in force between the contracting parties; Article 57 a) of the Agreement between the SFRY and the People's Republic of Hungary on Mutual Legal Assistance ("Official Gazette of the SFRY - International Agreements and Other Agreements", No. 3/68) reads: "Decisions from Article 56, paragraph (1) point a) and b) of this Agreement are recognized and will be enforced under the following conditions: a) if according to the law of the contracting

These agreements are particularly important for Bosnia and Herzegovina, bearing in mind that Brussels I Recast regime excludes third-country defendants from its scope of application, which will be discussed in detail in the next part of the paper.

3. Brussels I Recast Regulation Regime and Bosnia and Herzegovina

The recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments in the European Union is regulated by Regulation (EU) 1215/2012 of the European Parliament and the Council of December 12, 2012 on jurisdiction, recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments in civil and commercial matters (further on: Brussels I Recast Regulation).²⁶ The regime of the Brussels I Recast Regulation provides for a double standard regarding the application of the rules on the international jurisdiction of courts in civil and commercial matters. Namely, relations that have an inter-EU character are carried out in accordance with the rules of the Regulation. On the other hand, if it is a defendant with a domicile/seat outside the EU, the Brussels I Recast Regulation opens the door to national rules of private international law, including exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction.²⁷ The latter raises the question of whether the judgments of EU member state courts based on exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction could be recognized in third countries, including Bosnia and Herzegovina. The answer to this question depends on the legislative solutions of the state of recognition. If the state of recognition is not a party to the multilateral or bilateral convention which excludes the possibility of recognizing a judgment resulting from the “exorbitant jurisdiction” of that

party in which enforcement is requested, the court of the contracting party where the decision was made could act in that matter...”; Article 51 a) of the Agreement between the Federative People’s Republic of Yugoslavia and the Romanian People’s Republic on Legal Assistance dated October 18, 1960 (“Official Gazette of the FNRJ” - supplement No. 8/61, entered into force on October 1, 1961), reads: “Court decisions from Article 50 shall be recognized and enforced under the following conditions: a) if the law of the contracting party in which recognition or enforcement is requested does not exclude the jurisdiction of the court of the contracting party where the decision was made in that matter.

²⁶ OJL351, 20.12.2012, p. 1–32.

²⁷ Article 6 paragraph 1 Brussels I Recast Regulation reads: „If the defendant is not domiciled in a Member State, the jurisdiction of the courts of each Member State shall, subject to Article 18(1), Article 21(2) and Articles 24 and 25, be determined by the law of that Member State”.

Article 6 paragraph 2: „As against such a defendant, any person domiciled in a Member State may, whatever his nationality, avail himself in that Member State of the rules of jurisdiction there in force, and in particular those of which the Member States are to notify the Commission pursuant to point (a) of Article 76(1), in the same way as nationals of that Member State”.

court, it is important to have a rule in the PIL Act which prevents recognition of such judgments.²⁸ BH PIL Act does not contain such a rule. However, assuming that the bilateral agreements with France, Hungary and Romania are still in force,²⁹ the recognition and enforcement of court judgments based on exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction from these countries could be prevented. In relation to other EU national legislations, the system of recognition and enforcement in BH remains “unprotected”. Examples of exorbitant jurisdictional grounds could be: citizenship of the plaintiff, acquisition of property, performance of work, domicile or habitual residence of the plaintiff, submission initiating proceedings during the defendant’s temporary stay on the territory of a certain country, jurisdiction that is unilaterally determined by the plaintiff (e.g. on the invoice) without the consent of the defendant, jurisdiction based on the finding of the defendant’s product on the territory of a country, where that product caused damage, even though the defendant could not foresee that the product would be found on the territory of that country, imposition of a temporary or protective measure in order to decide on the merits, enforcement or registration of the judgment with the aim of establishing jurisdiction with regard to additional claims, etc.³⁰ To illustrate the problem in practice, we will use the example of the exorbitant ground of jurisdiction from Dutch law based on the issuance of an order for the seizure of the debtor’s property in order to decide on the merits (*forum arresti*).³¹ The main purpose of the seizure of the debtor’s property, which can be carried out over any form of property (money in bank accounts, shares in companies, claims against third parties, etc.) is to ensure the enforcement of

²⁸For example, the PIL Act of Montenegro and North Macedonia has such a provision.

²⁹V. supra f.n. 22. See also: Živković, M., Marjanović, S., *op. cit.*, p. 280.

³⁰Stryven, O., *Exorbitant Jurisdiction in the Brussels Convention*, (Electronic version) Jura Falconis Jg. 35, 1998-1999, Nummer 4, <https://www.law.kuleuven.be/apps/jura/public/art/35n4/stryven.pdf>, Retrieved 20.10.2023. Hacker, E., *Defining Exorbitant Jurisdiction*, (Electronic version) from: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2047113>, Retrieved 20.10.2023.

³¹Before the reform of the Code of Civil Procedure from 2001, the international jurisdiction of courts in the Netherlands was determined by the transposition of internal rules on local jurisdiction to cases with an international element, in accordance with the decisions of the Supreme Court of the Netherlands (HR 24.12.1915, NJ (1917), 417; HR 5.12.1940, NJ (1941), 313.) This principle of determining jurisdiction was satisfactory until there was an increase in the volume of international legal relations. The 2001 reform brought a number of useful changes, including a new set of rules on direct international jurisdiction of Dutch courts, but with this reform the Dutch legislator did not completely renounce the transposition of internal rules on local jurisdiction when resolving disputes with an international character. In this way, the principle of *forum arresti* is retained when determining the international jurisdiction of the Dutch court. Van Lith, H., *International Jurisdiction and Commercial Litigation, Uniform Rules for Contract Disputes*, T.M.C. Asser Press, 2009., p. 124.

the judgment that will be made. However, the imposition of such a protective measure can also mean the establishment of the international jurisdiction of the Dutch court to resolve the dispute on its merits.³² The ILA Principles on Provisional and Protective Measures in International Litigation³³ stipulate that the purpose of imposing these measures is to increase the protection of creditors in view of the international risk caused by differences in legal systems, procedures and practices. The goal is to stop the debtor from preventing the enforcement of the judgment by transferring assets, especially from bank accounts.³⁴ However, unlike the Dutch legislator who justifies the jurisdiction of the court to decide on the merits on the basis of *forum arresti*,³⁵ the ILA Principles on temporary and protective measures explicitly state in point 10 that “jurisdiction for the imposition of temporary and protective measures should be independent of the jurisdiction for resolving disputes on the merits”,³⁶ and that the fact that the court has determined a temporary and protective measure does not in itself mean that it is also competent to resolve the dispute on the merits, regardless whether the claim is related to the value of the seized property or not.³⁷ Although *forum arresti* is not explicitly mentioned in the list of exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction in the Draft Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Decisions from 1968, “... it was reasonable to assume that the recognition of a decision ren-

³² Conservatory arrest of assets in the Netherlands; obtaining security, putting pressure and/or creating jurisdiction, <https://www.vantraa.nl/en/know-how/conservatory-arrest-of-assets-in-the-netherlands-obtaining-security-putting-pressure-and-or-creating-jurisdiction/>, Retrieved 25.10.2023.

³³ International Law Association: The Helsinki Principles on Provisional and Protective Measures in International Litigation, *Rabels Zeitschrift für Ausländisches und Internationales Privatrecht*, Bd. 62, H. 1, 1998, str. 128-130.

³⁴ Juenger, F.K., *The ILA Principles on Provisional and Protective Measures*, *The American Journal of Comparative Law*, Vol. 45, No. 4, Symposium: Civil Procedure Reform in comparative Context, 1997., p. 941.

³⁵ Conservatory arrest of assets in the Netherlands; obtaining security, putting pressure and/or creating jurisdiction, <https://www.vantraa.nl/en/know-how/conservatory-arrest-of-assets-in-the-netherlands-obtaining-security-putting-pressure-and-or-creating-jurisdiction/>, Retrieved 25.10.2023.

³⁶ International Law Association: the Helsinki Principles on Provisional and Protective Measures in International Litigation, *Rabels Zeitschrift für Ausländisches und Internationales Privatrecht*, Bd. 62, H. 1, 1998, p. 128-130.

³⁷ Point 21 International Law Association: the Helsinki Principles on Provisional and Protective Measures in International Litigation, *Rabels Zeitschrift für Ausländisches und Internationales Privatrecht*, Bd. 62, H. 1, 1998, p. 128-130. Nygh, P., *Provisional and Protective Measures in International Litigation – The Helsinki Principles*, *Rabels Zeitschrift für Ausländisches und Internationales Privatrecht*, Bd. 62, H. 1, 1998, p. 115-122.

dered on this basis would also be excluded (in disputes between residents of the States of the Common Markets – authors’ remark”).³⁸ This basis for establishing international jurisdiction is not applied in relation to defendants from EU member states, in accordance with the Brussels regime of recognition and enforcement of court decisions in civil and commercial cases.³⁹ In relation to defendants from third countries, the application of the *forum arresti* rule comes into play when invoking other grounds does not result in the jurisdiction of the Dutch court, so it should be understood as a rule of “last resort”.⁴⁰ Thus, the jurisdiction of the Dutch court can be established on this basis with the cumulative fulfillment of several conditions: that the defendant (debtor) does not have a known domicile in the Netherlands, that the jurisdiction of the Dutch court cannot be based on another basis, that the property of the debtor that is the subject of the seizure, is located in the Netherlands, that in accordance with Article 767 of the Dutch Code of Civil Procedure there is no other way to obtain an enforcement order/enforceable title in the Netherlands, or that there is no agreement between the parties on the exclusive jurisdiction of a foreign court (e.g. a court in Bosnia and Herzegovina).⁴¹ The condition from Article 767 should be understood in such a way that the *forum arresti* rule does not apply if there is a concluded agreement between the Netherlands and another state that regulates the issue of mutual recognition and enforcement of court judgments.⁴² Since there is no such bilateral agreement between Bosnia and Herzegovina and the Netherlands, it is clear that the jurisdiction of the Dutch court may be established in accordance with the *forum arresti* rule. However, given the interpretation of the Supreme Court of the Netherlands in the *Gazprombank case* from 2014 and by fulfillment of the conditions explained in it,⁴³ there is the possibility

³⁸ De Winter, L.I., *Excessive Jurisdiction in Private International Law*, International and Comparative Law Quarterly, Vol 17., No. 3, 1968., p. 715.

³⁹ Pellis, L., *Forum Arresti: Aspecten van rechtmachtscheppend (vreemdelingen-) beslag in Europa*, 1993, pp. 7-15, cited according to: Van Lith, H., *International Jurisdiction and Commercial Litigation*, Uniform Rules for Contract Disputes, T.M.C. Asser Press, 2009., p. 137.

⁴⁰ *Op. cit.*, p. 136.

⁴¹ In this context, the mere existence of such an agreement in favor of the jurisdiction of a foreign court is sufficient, regardless of the possibility of its enforcement in the Netherlands. Van Lith, H., *op. cit.*, p. 138.

⁴² Van Lith, H., *op. cit.*, p. 137.

⁴³ HR 26. 9. 2014., ECLI:NL:HR:2014:2838. When assessing the possibility of recognizing a foreign court decision, the Dutch Supreme Court took into account the following criteria:

- (i) the jurisdiction of the court that issued the judgment that is acceptable according to international standards;
- (ii) the foreign decision was made in accordance with a legal procedure that ensures

of the recognition of the court judgment from BH in the Netherlands. Consequently, this would eliminate applying the *forum arresti* rule to establish the competence of the Dutch court to decide on the merits. If this were not the case, and the Dutch court makes a decision on the merits based on exorbitant jurisdiction, the question arises of the possibility of its recognition in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The question is particularly important for the reason that the value of the seized property, on the basis of which the *forum arresti* jurisdiction is based, does not necessarily coincide with the amount/value of the claim from the decision on the merits, which is why the need for recognition and enforcement on the debtor's property would arise in Bosnia and Herzegovina. This example shows how necessary it is to have a protective rule in domestic (BH) legislation, which would prevent the recognition of such decisions based on exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction.⁴⁴

4. Concluding remarks

Possible normative actions, which would prevent the effect of “exorbitant judgments” of EU member states in Bosnia and Herzegovina, can be divided into four groups. *First*, when the legal and political conditions for this are met in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the reform of the BH PIL Act should provide for a provision preventing the recognition of judgments made by the foreign courts on the basis of exorbitant jurisdiction. *Second*, a regional convention that would regulate the issue of mutual recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments, informally named the “Sarajevo Convention”,⁴⁵

compliance with fundamental procedural principles;

(iii) recognition of the foreign decision is not contrary to Dutch public policy; and

(iv) the foreign decision does not conflict with a decision of a Dutch court between the same parties or with a previous decision made by a foreign court between the same parties in a dispute with the same subject matter, provided that the previous decision is recognized in the Netherlands or meets the conditions for recognition. If the above conditions are met, the request for recognition is generally allowed. However, it is important to emphasize that in this system, developed in judicial practice, the foreign judgment is not declared “enforceable”, but a new judgment corresponding to the foreign judgment is pronounced in the proceedings before the Dutch court.

⁴⁴Of course, there remains the possibility that, depending on the circumstances of the specific case, the domestic court applies the public policy exception, and possibly refuses to recognize such a court judgment, which is based on an exorbitant ground of jurisdiction.

⁴⁵Meškić, Z., Radončić, Dž., *Brussels I Recast and the south-east Europe*, Revija za evropsko pravo, Vol 15 (1), 2013, p. 55-80.; Meškić, Z., *Regional Convention on Jurisdiction and the Mutual Recognition and Enforcement of Judgments in civil and Commercial Matters (Sarajevo Convention) – A Perspective of Bosnia and Herzegovina*, Liber Amicorum Gašo Knežević, Univerzitet u Beogradu – Pravni fakultet, Udruženje za arbitražno pravo, 2016, pp. 242-264.

did not result in success, although it had the potential to achieve the success that the Lugano Convention once achieved.⁴⁶ *Third*, in accordance with the EU's external competence regarding the conclusion of bilateral agreements with third countries as well as the practice of the Court of the EU,⁴⁷ EU member states lost the possibility of concluding bilateral agreements with third countries in areas that are internally regulated by binding EU acts.⁴⁸ Despite this, in certain areas of private international law and with the fulfillment of certain conditions, there is a possibility for member states to conclude bilateral agreements with third countries, even if the specific area is regulated by regulations at the EU level.^{49/50} In the context of the external jurisdiction of the EU,⁵¹ and the practice of the Court of the EU,⁵² it is important to consider the issue of bilateral cooperation between individual EU member states and third countries in the field of recognition and enforcement of foreign court decisions in civil and commercial cases. The position of the Court of the EU in the aforementioned ERTA decision is unequivocal when it says that "... every time the Community, in an effort to implement a common policy envisaged by the Treaty, adopts provisions establishing common rules regardless of the form they took, the member states no longer have the right to, acting individually or even collectively, assume obligations towards third countries".⁵³ The area of recognition and enforcement of foreign court

Alihodžić, J., Meškić, Z., Duraković, A., *op. cit.* p. 166. Jessel- Holst, C., *The Reform of Private International Law Acts in South East Europe, with Particular Regard to the West Balkan Region*, Anali Pravnog fakulteta u Zenici, Br. 18, God. 9, 2016, p. 142-143.

⁴⁶ The Convention of Lugano on Jurisdiction and the Recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and Commercial Matters, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 319, 9, 1988. o zaključenju ove konvencije v više u : Alihodžić, J., (2012)*op. cit.*, p. 52-55.

⁴⁷ ERTA, Case 22/70, Commission v. Council, 1971, ECLI:EU:C:1971:32. V. i Opinion 1/03, E.C.R. (2006) ECLI:EU:C:2006:81 i Opinion 1/13 OJ EU C 462, 22.12.2014, p. 4.

⁴⁸ Alihodžić, J., (2012)*op. cit.*, p. 46 -50.

⁴⁹ Alihodžić, J., *Uticao vanjske nadležnosti Evropske unije na sklapanje međunarodnih ugovora država članica u oblasti Međunarodnog privatnog prava – osvrt na Uredbu EZ br. 664/2009 i njen značaj za BiH*, Anali Pravnog fakulteta u Zenici, No. 6, year 3, 2010., p. 86-88.

⁵⁰ Proposal for a Decision of the European Parliament and of the Council on an authorization addressed to France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation and Commercial matters (COM/2023/65 final), and Proposal for a Council Decision on an authorization addressed to France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation concerning family law matters (COM/2023/64 final).

⁵¹ Article 3(2) Consolidated Version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (Official Journal of the European Union C 326/47.

⁵² ERTA.

⁵³ ERTA, paragraph 17.

judgments in civil and commercial matters at the EU level is covered by the Brussels I Recast regime. However, this Regulation does not contain a comprehensive set of rules regarding the recognition and enforcement of court decisions against defendants from third countries. In addition, the Regulation explicitly excludes the application of the rules on the international jurisdiction of the court in relation to defendants from third countries. Since the EU has not used its internal competence to enact regulations in this area, all EU member states are, according to the interpretation of the ERTA decision, free to enter into bilateral relations with third countries in the area of recognition and enforcement of foreign court decisions in civil and commercial matters (Article 4(j) and 81 TFEU).⁵⁴ This may result in the multiplication of differences between national legal systems in the area of recognition and enforcement of court judgments.⁵⁵ However, on the other hand, it is also an opportunity for Bosnia and Herzegovina to improve its own system in this area through bilateral agreements with some member states. This particularly refers to the possibility of refusing to recognize a judgment based on exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction, such as those based on forum arresti principle. Similar effects would be provided by the possibility of extending the rules of the Brussels I Recast Regulation regime to defendants domiciled/seated outside the EU.⁵⁶ Research conducted by the Asser Institute and the Erasmus School of Law showed that there is interest in such an initiative, where 44% of respondents (legal practitioners) declared that the rules on international jurisdiction should be fully unified at the EU level even in situations relating to defendants from third countries. Among the reasons cited in support of this position is certainly the fact that such rules would prevent the application of exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction, which would ultimately facilitate the system of recognition and enforcement of judgments in this area.⁵⁷ *Fourth*, there is a possibility of considering Bosnia and Herzegovina's accession to the 2019 Hague Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Court Judgments in Civil and Commercial Matters (hereinafter HC 2019⁵⁸),

⁵⁴ Alihodžić, J., Meškić, Z., Duraković, A., *op. cit.*, p. 168.

⁵⁵ Wilderspin, M., Vysoka, L., *The 2019 Hague Judgments Convention through European lenses*, *The Netherlands Journal of Private International Law*, 2020/1, p. 34-49.

⁵⁶ Burkhard Hess 'Reforming the Brussels I Regulation: Perspectives and Prospects' (2021) MPILux Research Paper Series 2021 (4) [www.mpi.lu], page access 24.10.2023.

⁵⁷ Kramer, X., Ontanu, A., de Rooij, M., Themeli, E., Hanemaayer, K, *The application of Brussels I (Recast) in the legal practice of EU Member States, Synthesis Report*, (Electronic version) from <https://www.asser.nl/media/5018/m-5797-ec-justice-the-application-of-brussels-1-09-outputs-synthesis-report.pdf>, Retrieved 26.10.2023.

⁵⁸ HC 2019 was adopted on July 2, 2019, and entered into force on September 1, 2023. Many papers have already been written about the importance and potential effects of HC 2019 in

which defines jurisdictional filters,⁵⁹ i.e. rules on indirect international jurisdiction, the fulfillment of which, along with assuming that the conditions for recognition from Article 7 HK 2019 are met,⁶⁰ makes the judgment of the country of origin become eligible for recognition.⁶¹

Summary

Future legislative action in the area of recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments in civil and commercial matters in BH is conditioned by various factors. Among them, the political ones dominate, especially when it comes to the lack of consensus for implementing the reform

the context of achieving international cooperation and legal security, and most of the authors of different countries, with minor or major objections, declared themselves in favor of joining this instrument, although there were also those who were not satisfied with the final solution of this document. Brand, R., *The Hague Judgments Convention in the United States: A "Game Changer" or a New Path to the Old Game?*, 82 *University of Pittsburgh Law Review*, 2021, p. 847, (Electronic version) from <http://ssrn.com/abstract=3747078>, Retrieved 21.10.2023. Van Loon, H., *Towards a Global Hague Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Judgments in Civil and Commercial Matters*, *Netherlands International Law Review*, No. 1, 2020. Rumenov, I., *Implications of the new 2019 Hague Convention on recognition and enforcement of foreign judgments on the national legal systems of countries in South Eastern Europe, EU and Member States – Legal and Economic Issues*, vol. 3, 2019, p. 385 – 404. Brand, R., *Jurisdiction and Judgments Recognition at the Hague Conference: Choices Made, Treaties Completed, and the Path Ahead*, *Netherlands International Law Review*, Volume 67, Issue 1, May 2020, p. 3-17; Weller, M., *The Jurisdictional Filters of the HCCH 2019 Judgments Convention*, *Yearbook of Private International Law XXI (2019/2020)*, 2020., p. 279. Schack, H., *HAVÜ Nein danke! Zur weltweiten Urteilsanerkennung und zum Jurisdiction Project der Haager Konferenz für IPR*, *Zeitschrift für Europäisches Privatrecht (ZEuP)*, 2023, p. 285-289.

⁵⁹The jurisdictional filters on which the system of recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments under the HC 2019 regime is based are regulated by Article 5 and 6 of the Convention. Đorđević, S., *Kratak osvrt na Hašku konvenciju o priznanju i izvršenju stranih sudskih odluka u građanskim ili trgovačkim stvarima iz 2019*, *Zbornik radova „Usklađivanje pravnog sistema Srbije sa standardima EU“*, Kragujevac, 2021, p. 411. Weller, M., *The Jurisdictional Filters of the HCCH 2019 Judgments Convention*, *Yearbook of Private International Law 2019/2020*, 2020, p. 279 – 308.

⁶⁰Jovanović, M., *Thou Shall (Not) Pass – Grounds for Refusal of Recognition and Enforcement under the 2019 Hague Judgments Convention*, *Yearbook of Private International Law 2019/2020*, 2020, p. 309 - 332.

⁶¹In the context of the recognition of judgments based on exorbitant grounds of jurisdiction, the provision of Article 17 HC 2019 is of particular importance according to which a State may declare that its courts may refuse to recognize or enforce a judgment given by a court of another Contracting State if the parties were resident in the requested State, and the relationship of the parties and all other elements relevant to the dispute, other than the location of the court of origin, were connected only with the requested State.

of the BH PIL Act. When it comes to legal reasons, one should keep in mind the fulfillment of obligations from the European integration process, including potential solutions in the field of recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments in civil and commercial matters. In this context, the authors of this text offer several solutions: reform of the BH PIL Act including the provision on the exorbitant jurisdiction of the foreign court, conclusion of bilateral agreements, extension of Brussels I Recast Regime to third-country defendants and/or accession to HC 2019.

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